

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF LEADERSHIP AND EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *Leadership and management are essential to the success of any organization. However, to be an effective leader, it is necessary to consider and understand the psychological aspects of these roles. Psychology plays a key role in determining a leader's ability to manage people and achieve goals.*

Keywords: *management activities, effective leader, effective management, group dynamics, psychological aspects of leadership, management decisions, self-awareness, self-development, management skills, leadership.*

It is important to suggest that the psychological aspects of leadership begin with self-awareness and self-development. A leader must be able to analyze his strengths and weaknesses, understand his emotions and control them. Self-esteem and self-confidence are very important because they influence the motivation of subordinates. Also important is a leader's emotional intelligence, which includes the ability to understand other people's emotions, manage one's own emotions, and communicate effectively with others. Emotional intelligence enables a leader to build trust, build effective relationships, and resolve conflict.

Additionally, understanding employee motivation is an important aspect of leadership. A leader must be able to motivate people based on their personal needs, values and beliefs. The psychological approach allows the manager to create incentives and rewards that effectively influence each employee.

Finally, understanding group dynamics and the ability to work as a team are also key psychological aspects of leadership. A leader must manage conflict, ensure cooperation, and keep each team member motivated. The ability to work in a team is an important skill for a leader. This requires not only the ability to lead people, but also an understanding of the psychology of group dynamics, as well as the ability to motivate, support and inspire team members. Working on this skill will greatly improve the effectiveness of the entire team.

The first and perhaps most important aspect of teamwork is communication. Clear and open communication with team members not only improves understanding of goals and objectives, but also allows for a better understanding of each member's needs and motivations. It is also important to listen to the opinions and suggestions of team members and take their opinions into account in the decision-making process.

Another important aspect is the ability to build trusting relationships. A leader who can build trust in the team can expect greater responsibility and effectiveness in the work of each team member. It also helps manage conflicts and uncertainties that inevitably arise in business activities. An important aspect of being able to work in a team is the ability to motivate. A good leader knows how to motivate his team to achieve goals. This may include creating goals, understanding how each team member's work relates to the overall goals of the organization, and creating incentives and rewards. The division of tasks and roles within the team is also important. The ability to

effectively distribute work among team members based on their strengths and professional skills is a key aspect of successful team performance.

If anyone randomly asks a hundred employees in different positions what is the most important factor in their success, most will answer that it is effective leadership. This answer reflects a common belief in the business world that leadership is a key component of organizational effectiveness, that is, an organization's ability to optimally achieve its goals. Such views are not unique to business: people believe that leadership plays a central role in politics, sports, city government and many other areas of human activity.

Effective leadership is a key factor in the success of an organization. Therefore, it is appropriate to consider the topic of leadership in more detail in a separate chapter.

Psychological aspects of preparation and making management decisions. An important task of a manager is to make management decisions and communicate them to the manager. The effectiveness of management activities depends on the correct and timely adoption of management decisions. As a rule, there is a goal - an ideal description of the desired state of the control object or the result of the activity. If the actual state does not match the desired state, there is a problem. The tool for solving this problem is a management decision, which is a recipe for action, a list of measures to bring the system to the desired state. The process of making a management decision begins with the emergence of a problem situation and ends with the development of a solution.

The management decision must meet the following requirements:

- have a clear goal (not cause uncertainty and doubt among subordinates);
- be reasonable and consistent (in accordance with internal and external conditions, as well as previous and future decisions);
- be qualified (based on legal requirements, taking into account the responsibilities and rights of the manager and subordinate);
- be clear (have an addressee, deadlines, answer questions about what, to whom, when, where and when to do);
- be timely and effective.

Making and making decisions is a psychological process. There are three approaches to decision making:

- intuitive - decisions are made based on a sense of correctness, without analyzing all the pros and cons;
- a decision based on judgments - a choice based on knowledge or accumulated experience (advantages: speed of the process of selecting alternatives, disadvantages: does not work in cases where the leader has no analogue in his past experience);
- rational - analytically sound.

The process of preparing and making a decision includes the following stages:

1. Indicative – identifying a problem situation and determining the goal of its solution;
2. Information – collection, processing and analysis of information on the problem;
3. Stage of development and decision-making: formation of a set of alternative solutions with the possible participation of the executor of the future decision (Lickert's law - the higher the quality and accuracy of the decision, the more direct participants in the process). performing tasks involved in decision making); evaluate alternative solutions based on their advantages, disadvantages and possible consequences; choosing the optimal solution;

4. Organizational stage – communication of decisions and deadlines to executors, appointment of responsible persons, briefing;

5. Control stage - accounting and control of the execution of the decision is usually assigned to the group that prepared the decision.

The weakest points in preparation and decision-making are their quality and lack of control. Management decisions are not implemented for the following reasons:

- if previous ones are not taken into account in newly adopted decisions;
- making decisions that do not have specific content;
- setting unrealistic deadlines;
- lack of a procedure for agreeing on a number of decisions with the executors.

In conclusion, it can be suggested that the ability to work in a team requires the leader not only to understand his own skills and characteristics, but also the ability to lead, motivate, communicate and establish trusting relationships with team members. All this together helps to create a professional, efficient and motivated team capable of achieving its goals. Psychological aspects of leadership and management play an important role in achieving success in any organization. Understanding oneself, others and group dynamics allows a leader to effectively motivate, influence and manage their team to achieve their goals.

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